

CRYSTALLINE COMPONENTS OF THE SEEDS OF *HERACLEUM NEPALENSE*
(N. O. UMBELLIFERAE). PART I *

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Six crystalline components have been isolated from the seeds of *Heracleum nepalense*. The first component of m. p. 188-89° is found identical with bergapten. The second component having m. p. 157-58° and mol. formula $C_{12}H_{18}O_4$ is isomeric with bergapten. The third component melts at 120-24° and possesses properties and structure identical with byakangelicin. The fourth component melting at 204° is found identical with allo-imperatorin. The other two components melt respectively at 202°-204° and at 231°.

H. Nepalense (N. O. Umbelliferae) is a small shrubby plant growing in the region of Nepal and extended to Bhutan at an altitude of 5000 to 12000 feet. It flowers early in September after which it gradually withers away. The seeds were collected from the district of Darjeeling.

The dry crushed seeds have been extracted with ether in a soxhlet and from the ethereal extract five neutral crystalline compounds and an acidic crystalline substance have been isolated :

(i) A colourless compound (m. p. 188-89°) crystallising in long, silky needles has been isolated in 0.025—0.030% yield. It does not contain any phenolic OH group and it apparently behaves like a coumarin.

The analytical data are in agreement with the formula $C_{11}H_8O_3$ (OMe). The molecular weight by titration, has been found to be 215.6, agreeing with the formula, $C_{12}H_8O_4$ (216). The properties of the compound, as also the observed analytical values resemble those of bergapten (5-methoxy-furo-2': 3': 7: 6-coumarin), m. p. 191-92° (mixed m. p. with authentic sample same).

(ii) The second compound (m. p. 157-58°) crystallising in colourless needles, has been isolated in 0.015% yield. Phenolic hydroxyl appears to be absent. It behaves like a coumarin.

The C-H values and the methoxyl estimation agree with the formula, $C_{12}H_8O_4$ and hence it is isomeric with bergapten. It is, however, remarkable to note that the substance is transformed into bergapten when refluxed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide in a water-bath for 1 hour. Probably the compound is a stereoisomer of bergapten.

(iii) The third component, forming light yellow shining flakes (m. p. 120-24°), has been isolated in a fairly good yield, being 0.10% of the weight of the dry seeds.

A close inspection of the properties (vide experimental) of the compound suggests the presence of a coumarin nucleus. Analytical data are in agreement with the formula, $C_{17}H_{18}O_7$. Although it does not respond to ferric reaction, it contains two hydroxyl groups as it readily gives a diacetyl derivative. One methoxyl group is also present. Hence the compound may be written as $C_{16}H_{13}O_4(OH)_2(OCH_3)$. We have now to account for the remaining four oxygen atoms. If the substance under investigation is a furo-coumarin, three oxygen atoms may be accounted for. It occurred to us that the remaining oxygen atom might be present as an oxy-alkylenated group.

Späth and co-workers (*Ber.*, 1933, 66B, 914) have shown that the ether linkage in the oxy-alkylenated coumarins can be cleaved by the action of concentrated sulphuric

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and glacial acetic acids when the phenyl complex is eliminated creating a phenolic hydroxyl group in place of ethereal oxygen. When the above compound is heated with acetic-sulphuric acid mixture, a phenol (m. p. 218-19°) is obtained.

The analytical data of the phenol (m. p. 219°) agree with the molecular formula, $C_{12}H_8O_5$, and it contains one methoxyl group. On methylation it furnishes a dimethyl ether (m. p. 149°). If the phenol is a hydroxy derivative of a furo-coumarin, we can account for all the oxygen atoms. A search for the melting points of the derivatives of the known hydroxy furo-coumarins showed that the melting points of the dimethyl ether of the phenol and of isopimpinellin (Wessely and Kallab, *Monats.*, 1932, 59, 161) were identical. The identity has finally been established by a direct comparison of the two compounds.

The isolation of isopimpinellin from the phenol conclusively proves that the phenol is a furo-coumarin, and since it contains a methoxy group and a free phenolic hydroxyl group, it is either (I) or (II).

The degradation of the compound to a phenolic substance which forms isopimpinellin by methylation leaves no doubt that the compound under investigation is a furo-coumarin derivative.

A search of the literature revealed a furo-coumarin, byakangelicin, isolated from the root of *Angelica glabra*, Makino (Japanese drug 'Byakusi') by Noguti and Kawanami (*Ber.*, 1938, 71B, 344, 1428) (cf. also Bose and Chaudhuri, *Ann. Biochem. Expt. Med.*, 1946, 6, 1) having the same molecular formula $C_{17}H_{14}O_7$ and almost identical m. p. 125-26°. Byakangelicin has been assigned the formula (III) and it seems probable to us that our furo-coumarin from the seeds of *H. nepalense* is identical with byakangelicin.

The properties and the reactions of our product are found to be similar to those of byakangelicin. The crystallised product $C_{17}H_{14}O_7, H_2O$ from ethyl acetate, benzene or alcohol melts at 120-24° (lit. m. p. 117-19°), but when dried over P_2O_5 in vacuum at 110° for 8 hours, it melts at 124-26°.

The derivatives of our product appear to be identical with those of byakangelicin

as shown below. Direct comparison of our substances with byakangelicin and its derivatives has not been possible in the absence of authentic specimens.

Derivatives.	Comp., m. p. 120-24° C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₇ , H ₂ O m. p. 112°	Byakangelicin C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₇ , H ₂ O m. p. 118-19°
Diacetate Phenol obtained by glacial acetic acid and sulphuric acid	218-19°	212°.

(vi) The fourth component, forming dull yellow shining plates (m. p. 229°) has been isolated in 0.04% yield. It is neutral to litmus, soluble in cold dilute alkali and does not respond towards ferric chloride. The substance is soluble in cold concentrated sulphuric acid with a permanent deep yellow colour. Thus the compound seems to be a coumarin.

Analytical values agree with the formula C₁₆H₁₄O₄. It contains one free phenolic hydroxyl group as it furnishes a light yellow monoacetyl derivative (m. p. 137°) and a monomethyl ether (m. p. 113°). Methoxyl group is absent. A study of its properties reveals similarity with allo-imperatorin (IV), m. p. 233°, which has been obtained by Späth (*Ber.*, 1933, 66B, 1137) by distillation of imperatorin (V) at a pressure of 0.5 mm. of Hg.

It may be noted in this connection that allo-imperatorin was obtained synthetically by Späth and co-workers, and it has for the first time been isolated from a natural source. A direct comparison of m. p. and mixed m. p. with an authentic sample of allo-imperatorin and also the mixed m. p. of the methyl ether with an authentic sample of the methyl ether of allo-imperatorin establishes its identity with allo-imperatorin.

Product isolated	Synthetic product	
m. p. 228-29°	m. p. 229°	mixed m. p. 229°
Methyl ether, m. p. 113°	m. p. 113°.5	mixed m. p. 113°

The constitution of the remaining two components, (i) m. p. 202-204° and (ii) m. p. 231° still remains to be determined.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The dried and powdered seeds (2.2 kg.) were extracted in a soxhlet with ether (16 hours). The deep green extract, which appeared to be brown in the transmitted light, was freed from the solvent by distillation. The oily residue deposited a light yellow solid on keeping overnight. The whole mass was then treated with benzene (200 c. c.), shaken well and filtered in a pump. Much difficulty was experienced during filtration as the oily product was originally contaminated with some water. The yellow residue

(A) was washed several times with benzene to remove associated oils and the filtrate (B) was collected. The following six constituents have been isolated :

(i) *Purification of the residue (A) : Isolation of Bergapten.*—The yellow residue (A) was freed from the adhering solvent in an air-oven. It was crystallised from rectified spirit as colourless needles, m. p. 185°. Successive crystallisations from benzene and ethyl acetate raised the m. p. to 188.89°. The product distilled at 150-160°/0.1 mm., m. p. 188-89° even after recrystallisation from benzene, ethyl acetate and alcohol ; yield 0.65 g.

Isolation of a crystalline Compound of m. p. 157-58°.—The alcoholic mother-liquor from the residue (A) was concentrated and the second crop of crystals obtained was of crude bergapten. Finally the alcoholic mother-liquor was diluted with water and eventually dull yellow needles of m. p. 157-58° were obtained from dilute alcohol. The product was distilled in *vacuo* (140-150°/0.1 mm.). The m. p. did not rise on recrystallisation from ethyl acetate and benzene ; yield 0.33 g.

Treatment of the filtrate (B) : Isolation of Byakangelicin.—Petroleum ether (b. p. 40-60°) was added to the filtrate (B) to turbidity and the mixture was kept in a frigidaire overnight. A dark pasty solid separated and it was filtered, washed with benzene to remove adhering oil and crystallised twice from dilute alcohol as light yellow needles, m. p. 117-20°. The filtrate (C) containing benzene and petroleum ether was collected. The substance was further purified through successive crystallisations from benzene and ethyl acetate, m. p. 120-24°. Finally the product was subjected to vacuum sublimation and the yellow solid distilling at 200-210°/0.1 mm. had the melting point 120-24°, which was unchanged on crystallisation from benzene and ethyl acetate. The alcoholic mother-liquor when diluted with water deposited a second crop of impure byakangelicin. Benzene and ethyl acetate mother-liquors deposited on concentration a further quantity of the same substance. Total yield is 2.2 g.

Isolation of allo-Imperatorin.—The filtrate (C) was freed from the mixture of solvents by distillation and the residual oil was subjected to the method of Späth and Socias (*Ber.*, 1934, 67, 59).

The oil was cooled to about 15° and to it were added 200 c. c. of 20% methyl alcoholic potash with constant shaking. The mixture was allowed to stand for an hour at the same temperature and then poured into 1.5 litres of ice-water. The mixture was then extracted five times with ether to remove unsaponifiable matter. The alkaline aqueous portion was acidified with hydrochloric acid (Congo red) and allowed to stand overnight. A dark, thick oil mixed with crystalline solid separated.

The oily layer was separated, filtered in a pump, washed with ether and the residue (D) collected. The filtrate was freed from the solvent and the residual oil was kept overnight, whereby a pasty solid was obtained. The pasty solid was treated with a little alcohol and filtered, the filtrate being rejected. The residue was twice crystallised from alcohol and finally from glacial acetic acid as yellow shining plates, m. p. 229°, yield 0.88 g.

Purification of the residue (D) : Isolation of two compounds of m. p. 231° and 202-204°.—The residue (D) was crystallised three times from alcohol as pale yellow

shining plates, m. p. 200-204°. A second crop of crystals was obtained by diluting the alcoholic mother-liquors.

The crystalline compound of m. p. 200-204° was a mixture of two compounds, one being readily soluble in alkali carbonates and bicarbonates, caustic alkali and in ammonia. Consequently the substance was treated with a solution of sodium bicarbonate and kept overnight. The insoluble portion was filtered off, washed with water, and crystallised from ethyl acetate as light yellow needles, m. p. 231°. Further crystallisation from alcohol did not raise the melting point. The alkaline filtrate was acidified with hydrochloric acid, the colourless solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol as colourless shining plates, m. p. 202-204°. The melting point did not rise on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid, yield 3 g.

Identity of the Compound of m. p. 188-89° with Bergapten.—The substance is neutral to litmus and indifferent towards ferric chloride. It is insoluble in dilute aqueous alkali, but soluble in concentrated sulphuric acid with a deep yellow colour. An alcoholic solution of the substance turns yellow on addition of aqueous alkali and the alkaline solution remains clear on dilution. Original substance is recovered on acidification of the alkaline solution. The mixed m. p. with an authentic sample of bergapten is 188-89°. (Found in a sample dried over P_2O_5 in vacuum at 110-15° : C, 66.80; H, 3.98; OMe, 14.54; M. W. 218.6. Calc. for $C_{12}H_8O_4$: C, 66.66; H, 3.70; OMe; 14.35 per cent. M. W., 216).

Constitution of the Compound (m. p. 157-58°).—The compound is insoluble in dilute aqueous alkali and gives no coloration with ferric chloride, showing the probable absence of phenolic hydroxyl group. The substance dissolves in alcoholic potassium hydroxide from which the original substance may be recovered on acidification. (Found in a sample dried over P_2O_5 in vacuum at 100°-105° : C, 66.10; H, 3.80; OMe, 14.76. Calc. for $C_{12}H_8O_4$: C, 66.66; H, 3.70; OMe, 14.35 per cent).

Action of Alcoholic Potash on the Compound (m. p. 157-58°) : Isomerisation to Bergapten.—The substance (0.1 g.) was refluxed with moderately concentrated alcoholic potash for 1 hour on a water-bath. The solution was then cooled, diluted with water and acidified. The solid thus obtained, crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 188-89° (mixed m. p. with an authentic specimen of bergapten, 188-89°).

Identity of the Compound (m. p. 120-24°) with Byakangelicin.—The substance is readily soluble in alcohol, benzene, chloroform and it crystallises from ethyl acetate in yellow shining flakes. It is neutral and gives no coloration with ferric chloride. It dissolves in cold concentrated sulphuric acid with a deep yellow colour. It is readily soluble in cold and boiling alcoholic potash from which the original compound is recovered on acidification. (Found in a sample dried over P_2O_5 in vacuum for 8 hours at 110° : C, 61.35; H, 5.85; OMe, 9.83. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{18}O_7$: C, 61.07; H, 5.38; OMe, 9.28 per cent).

Diacetyl Byakangelicin.—The substance (0.1 g.) was gently refluxed with acetic anhydride (5 c. c.) and dry pyridine (2 drops) for 2 hours. The mixture was cooled, diluted with water, heated on a steam-bath for 10 minutes. The solid separating was crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless silky needles, m. p. 112°. (Found in a

sample dried over P_2O_5 in vacuum for 2 hours at $85-90^\circ$: C, 60.03 ; H, 5.44. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{12}O_2$: C, 60.28 ; H, 5.26 per cent).

Action of glacial acetic acid and sulphuric acid on Byakangelicin: Isolation of a Phenol (m. p. 219°).—The substance (0.50 g.) was dissolved in a mixture of glacial acetic acid (12 c. c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (12 drops) and the solution was just heated to boiling under reflux for 30 minutes. The mixture was cooled and diluted with water. The yellow solid was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol as yellow silky needles, m. p. 219° . This substance is readily soluble in dilute aqueous alkali but does not respond to ferric reaction. (Found in a sample dried over P_2O_5 in vacuum at $110-15^\circ$: C, 61.98; H, 3.64; OMe, 13.70. Calc. for $C_{12}H_8O_3$: C, 62.07 ; H, 3.45; OMe, 13.36 per cent).

Action of Methyl Iodide on the above Phenol: Formation of isoPimpinellin.—A solution of the phenol (0.10 g.) in dry acetone was refluxed with methyl iodide (5 c. c.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g.) for 2 hours on a water-bath. The solution was then cooled, filtered, freed from the solvent and the residue crystallised from alcohol as yellow shining needles, m. p. 149° . The methyl ether is insoluble in cold alkali. The mixed m. p. with the authentic specimen of *isopimpinellin* is also 149° . (Found in a sample dried over P_2O_5 in vacuum at 100° for 2 hours : OMe, 25.14. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{10}O_2$: OMe, 25.20 per cent).

Identity of the Compound (m. p. 229°) *with allo-Imperatorin*.—It was obtained as yellow shining plates, readily soluble in ethyl acetate, benzene but sparingly soluble in alcohol and glacial acetic acid. It is neutral to litmus, and does not give any coloration with ferric chloride. It is soluble in cold and boiling aqueous alkali from which the original substance is recovered on acidification. It is insoluble in alkali carbonate and bicarbonate but soluble in cold concentrated sulphuric acid with a deep yellow colour. It melts at 229° when mixed with an authentic specimen of *allo-imperatorin*. (Found in a sample dried over P_2O_5 in vacuum at 110° : C, 70.68; H, 5.15. Calc. for $C_{16}H_{14}O_4$: C, 71.11 ; H, 5.18 per cent).

Acetylation of allo-Imperatorin.—The acetyl derivative was prepared with acetic anhydride and pyridine in the usual manner. The solid crystallised from dilute alcohol as colourless shining flakes, m. p. 137° . It melts at 136° when mixed with an authentic sample of the acetyl derivative of *allo-imperatorin*.

Methylation of allo-Imperatorin.—The methyl ether was prepared with methyl iodide in the usual manner. The product crystallised from dilute alcohol as pale yellow silky needles, m. p. 113° . It is insoluble in dilute aqueous alkali. It also melts at 113° when mixed with an authentic sample of the methyl ether of *allo-imperatorin*. (Found in a sample dried over P_2O_5 in vacuum at 90° : C, 71.60 ; H, 5.46 ; OMe, 10.80. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 71.83 ; H, 5.63 ; OMe, 10.91 per cent).

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